

ANIQ INTEGRALLARNI O'QITISHDA SODDADAN MURAKKABGA
TOMON METODINI QO'LLASH

TTYSI assistant Tojinorova Maxliyo Murodjon qizi

TTYSI assistant Axmedov Quanishbek Nizamiddinovich

TTYSI talaba Mamajonova Malika Abdullo qizi

Matematika fani fanlari ichida "FAN" xisoblanadi. Undan fikrlash, tahlil qilish, dunyoqarashni shakllantirish, isbotlash, mulohaza qilish kabi insonning eng yuksak fazilatlarini tarkib topadi. Matematika o'qitishda ko'zda tutilgan masalalarni asoslash nima uchun matematika o'qitiladi, o'rgatiladi degan savollarga javob berish bilan uning maqsadini asoslashimiz mumkin.

a) Aniq integral yordamida **yassi shaklning yuzlarini** hisoblash mumkin va bu quyidagicha amalgam oshiriladi. $y = f(x)$ funksiya grafigi, $x = a$, $x = b$ ikkita to'g'ri chiziq va Ox o'qi bilan chegaralangan egri chizikli trapetsiyaning yuzini ($f(x) \geq 0$).

$S = \int_a^b f(x) dx = \int_a^b y dx$ formula bo'yicha hisoblanishini bilamiz.

$y = f_2(x)$ va $y = f_1(x)$ egri chiziqlar bilan chegaralangan soha yuzasi quyidagi formula bilan topiladi: $S = \int_a^b [f_2(x) - f_1(x)] dx$. (4)

b) **Aylanma jismlarining hajmini hisoblash.** Uzluksiz $y = f(x)$ egri chiziq, absissalar o'qi hamda, $x = a$, $x = b$ ($a < b$) to'g'ri chiziqlar bilan chegaralangan egri chizikli trapetsiyaning Ox o'qi atrofida aylantirishdan hosil

bo'lgan jismning hajmi $V = \pi \int_a^b [f(x)]^2 dx$ formula bo'yicha hisoblanadi.

c) **Yassi egri chiziq yoyi uzunliklarini hisoblash.** $y = f(x)$ funksiya $[a, b]$ kesmada silliq bo'lsin. U holda bu egri chiziqning $x = a, x = b$ to'g'ri chiziqlari bilan chegaralangan yoyining uzunligi

$$l = \int_a^b \sqrt{1 + (y')^2} dx \quad \text{formula bo'yicha hisoblanadi.}$$

d) **Aylanish jismlari sirtining yuzini hisoblash.** $x = a, x = b$ to'g'ri chiziqlari bilan chegaralangan $y = f(x)$ egri chiziqning Ox o'q atrofida

aylanishidan hosil bo'lgan sirt yuzi S_x , $S_x = 2\pi \int_a^b y \sqrt{1 + (y')^2} dx$ formula bo'yicha

topiladi. Masalan, talabalarga bosqichlab, soddadan murakkabga qarab matematika o'rgatiladi. Aniq integralni aniq hisoblashning asosiy yagona usuli, integral ostidagi funksiya uchun boshlang'ich funksiya ni aniqlash va so'ngra Nyuton – Leybnits formulasini qo'llashdir. Uni quyidagicha yozish mumkin:

$$\int_a^b f(x) dx = F(x) \Big|_a^b = F(b) - F(a). \quad \text{Shunday qilib, aniq integralni bevosita integral}$$

yig'indi limiti sifatida emas, balki N'yuton – Leybnits formulasi bo'yicha hisoblash mumkin.

Aniq integralda o'zgaruvchini almashtirish quyidagicha amalga

oshiriladi: $f(x)$ funksiya $[a; b]$ kesmada uzluksiz va $\int_a^b f(x) dx$ integral berilgan

bo'lsin. $x = \varphi(t)$ almashtirish bilan integrallash o'zgaruvchisi t bo'lgan yangi aniq

integralga keladi. Bunda $\varphi(t), \varphi'(t)$ funksiya lar $[\alpha; \beta]$ kesmada,

$\varphi(\alpha) = a, \varphi(\beta) = b$, uzluksiz bo'lishi kerak.

$$\text{Bu shartlar bajarilganda, } \int_a^b f(x) dx = \int_{\alpha}^{\beta} f(\varphi(t)) \varphi'(t) dt \text{ formula o'rinli bo'ladi.}$$

Aniq integralda bo'laklab integrallash quyidagicha amalgam oshiriladi:

$u(x)$ va $v(x)$ funksiya lar $[a;b]$ kesmada differentsiallanuvchi funksiya lar bo'lsin. U holda aniq integralda bo'laklab integrallash quyidagi formula

$$\int_a^b u(x) dv(x) = u(x)v(x) \Big|_a^b - \int_a^b v(x) du(x)$$

bo'yicha amalga oshiriladi. Agar:

1) $f(x)$ funksiya toq, ya'ni $f(-x) = -f(x)$ bo'lsa, u holda $\int_{-a}^a f(x) dx = 0$;

2) $f(x)$ funksiya juft, ya'ni $f(-x) = f(x)$ bo'lsa, u holda $\int_{-a}^a f(x) dx = 2 \int_0^a f(x) dx$.

Aniq integrallarni hisoblash ko'nikmasini quyidagicha bosqichma bosqich shakllantirish mumkin.

- Bevosita integrallash usuliga doir misollar ko'rib chiqiladi.

1. $\int_1^2 x^3 dx = \frac{x^4}{4} \Big|_1^2 = \frac{1}{4}(2^4 - 1^4) = \frac{1}{4}(16 - 1) = \frac{1}{4}15 = \frac{15}{4}$;

2. $\int_0^\pi \sin x dx = -\cos x \Big|_0^\pi = -(\cos \pi - \cos 0) = -(-1 - 1) = 2$.

3. $\int_0^1 \frac{dx}{1+x^2} = \arctg x \Big|_0^1 = \arctg 1 - \arctg 0 = \frac{\pi}{4}$

- Integral ostiga kiritish orqali hisoblash.

4. $\int_1^3 2(x+2)^2 dx = 2 \int_1^3 (x+2)^2 d(x+2) = \frac{2}{3}(x+2)^3 \Big|_1^3 = \frac{2}{3}((3+2)^3) = \frac{2}{3}(125 - 27) = \frac{2}{3} \cdot 98 = \frac{196}{3}$;

- O'zgaruvchini almashtirish orqali hisoblash.

5. $\int_3^8 \frac{x}{\sqrt{1+x}} dx = \begin{cases} \sqrt{1+x} = t & x=3 \text{ da } t=2 \\ 1+x=t^2 & x=8 \text{ da } t=3 \\ x=t^2-1 & \end{cases} = \int_2^3 \frac{(t^2-1) \cdot t dt}{t} = 2 \int_2^3 dt = 2 \left(\frac{t^3}{3} - t \right) \Big|_2^3 =$
 $= 2(9 - 3 - \frac{8}{3} + 2) = \frac{32}{3}$

$$6. \int_0^1 \frac{x dx}{x^2+1} = \left. \begin{array}{l} x^2+1=t \\ 2x dx = dt \\ x \rightarrow 0, t \rightarrow 1 \\ x \rightarrow 1, t \rightarrow 2 \end{array} \right| = \int_1^2 \frac{\frac{dt}{2}}{t} = \frac{1}{2} \int_1^2 \frac{dt}{t} = \frac{1}{2} \ln|t| \Big|_1^2 = \frac{1}{2} [\ln 2 - \ln 1] = \frac{1}{2} [\ln 2] = \ln \sqrt{2};$$

$$7. \int_0^{\pi/3} \cos^2 x \sin x dx = \left. \begin{array}{l} \cos x = t \\ \sin x dx = -dt \\ x \rightarrow 0 \quad \partial a \quad t \rightarrow 1 \\ x \rightarrow \frac{\pi}{3} \quad \partial a \quad t \rightarrow \frac{1}{2} \end{array} \right| = - \int_1^{1/2} t^2 dt = \frac{t^3}{3} \Big|_1^{1/2} = \frac{1}{3} \left[1^3 - \left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^3 \right] = \frac{1}{3} \left(1 - \frac{1}{8} \right) = \frac{1}{3} \cdot \frac{7}{8} = \frac{7}{24};$$

• Bo‘laklab integrallash orqali hisoblash.

$$8. \int_0^1 \arctg x dx = \left. \begin{array}{l} u = \arctg x, \quad dv = dx \\ du = \frac{dx}{1+x^2}; \quad v = x \end{array} \right| = x \cdot \arctg x \Big|_0^1 - \int_0^1 x \cdot \frac{dx}{1+x^2} = x \cdot \arctg x \Big|_0^1 - \frac{1}{2} \ln|1+x^2| \Big|_0^1 =$$

$$1 \cdot \arctg 1 - 0 \cdot \arctg 0 - \frac{1}{2} [\ln(1+1^2) - \ln(1+0)] = \frac{\pi}{4} - \frac{1}{2} (\ln 2 - \ln 1) = \frac{\pi}{4} - \frac{1}{2} \ln 2 = \frac{\pi}{4} - \ln \sqrt{2};$$

$$9. \int_0^1 x \cdot e^x dx = \left. \begin{array}{l} u = x; \quad du = dx \\ dv = e^x dx \quad v = e^x \end{array} \right| = x \cdot e^x \Big|_0^1 - \int_0^1 e^x \cdot dx = x \cdot e^x \Big|_0^1 - e^x \Big|_0^1 = 1 \cdot e^1 - 0 \cdot e^0 -$$

$$- e^1 + e^0 = e - e + 1 = 1;$$

$$10. \int_1^e x \ln^2 x dx = \left. \begin{array}{l} u = \ln^2 x, \quad du = \frac{2}{x} \ln x dx \\ dv = x dx, \quad v = \frac{x^2}{2} \end{array} \right| = \frac{x^2}{2} \ln x \Big|_1^e + \frac{1}{2} \int_1^e x dx = \left. \begin{array}{l} u = \ln^2 x, \quad du = \frac{2}{x} \ln x dx \\ dv = x dx, \quad v = \frac{x^2}{2} \end{array} \right| =$$

$$= \frac{x^2}{2} \ln x \Big|_1^e + \frac{1}{2} \int_1^e x dx = \frac{e^2}{2} - \frac{e^2}{2} + \frac{e^2}{4} - \frac{1}{4} = \frac{1}{4} (e^2 - 1)$$

$$11. \int_0^{\pi/3} \cos^2 x \sin x dx = \left. \begin{array}{l} \cos x = t \\ \sin x dx = -dt \\ x \rightarrow 0 \quad \partial a \quad t \rightarrow 1 \\ x \rightarrow \frac{\pi}{3} \quad \partial a \quad t \rightarrow \frac{1}{2} \end{array} \right| = - \int_1^{1/2} t^2 dt = \frac{t^3}{3} \Big|_1^{1/2} = \frac{1}{3} \left[1^3 - \left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^3 \right] = \frac{1}{3} \left(1 - \frac{1}{8} \right) = \frac{1}{3} \cdot \frac{7}{8} = \frac{7}{24};$$

Xulosa qilib aytganda, ta’limning o‘quvchilarga mos bo‘lishi qoidasida ta’limning ikki tomoni e’tiborda tutiladi: a) o‘quv materiallarining xarakteri mazmuni va hajmi o‘rganuvchilarining yosh xususiyatlariga mos bo‘lishi;

b) bilim hajmi o'quvchilarning saviyasiga mos bo'lishi lozim. Ta'limning bilim oluvchilarga mos bo'lishi "Osondan qiyinga qarab borish", "Ma'lumdan noma'lumga qarab borish", "Soddadan murakkabga qarab borish" qoidalarga asoslanilishi kerak.

Fodalanilgan adabiyotlar

1. Azlarov T. A., Mansurov X. T. "*Matematik analiz*". I, II tom 1994, 1995.2. G. Xudoyberganov, A. Vorisov, X. Mansurov. «*Matematik analiz*». Nasaf nashriyoti. 2003 yil.
3. A. Sadullayev, X. Mansurov, G. Xudoyberganov, A. Varisov, R. Fulomov "*Matematik analiz kursidan misol va masalalar to'plami*" 1,2 tom. "O'zbekiston", 1993, 1995.
4. Tuychiyev T. T., Djumaboyev D. X. "*Matematik analiz fanidan 1- kurs talabalari uchun laboratoriya ishlari*", T. "Universitet" 2003.

